

The Influence of Price and Brand Quality on Market Orientation is mediated by Social Media Marketing

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ABSTRACT: This research analyzes the factors that influence market orientation in the retail industry, especially supermarkets in Batam City. People tend to want convenience and comfort in shopping, leading to a preference for supermarkets that are clean and modern and provide a variety of products. Batam, as a strategic industrial city, has tight retail competition with the development of minimarkets such as Indomaret and Alfamart. The research used a quantitative method with a questionnaire distributed to 266 respondents, measuring variables such as price, brand loyalty, product quality, service quality, stock, social media marketing, and market orientation. The research results show that price and stock have a significant influence on market orientation, while brand loyalty, service quality and social media marketing have varying influences. Product quality has a significant effect on social media marketing, but social media marketing is not significant on market orientation. The limitation of this research lies in the limited variable focus. It is recommended that further research add variables such as customer satisfaction, purchase intention, and consumer decision to expand understanding of the factors that influence market orientation.

KEYWORDS: Brand Quality, Market Orientation, Product Quality, Stock, Social Media Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

People have a desire to fulfill their rational and never-satisfied needs. Humans have 3 types of basic (primary) needs, namely clothing needs in the form of clothing, food needs such as food and drink to live, and finally housing needs such as housing to survive, with these basic needs it can affect economic growth in Indonesia.

As the era develops, people want everything to be done and completed easily and quickly so that people can do other work. With the desire for people with a practical lifestyle, this has caused people to be lazy to shop in traditional markets and made people prefer to shop at supermarkets because the shopping atmosphere in supermarkets can be said to be much more comfortable, clean, modern, and the availability of products and brands is more varied to meet people's needs (Vicky & Ananda, 2023).

Indonesia has various provinces and islands, one of which is Batam City which is in the Riau Islands Province. Batam is in the western part of Indonesia which is located close to neighboring countries, namely Singapore and Malaysia because of its strategic location, Batam City is nicknamed an industrial city because its area is on the Indonesian border which makes it easy for foreign products to enter through personal purchases (Liusudarso et al., 2022).

Supermarkets are a form of retail or retail stores that provide various types of products and daily necessities for consumers, supermarkets usually have a large sales area and provide products in various categories such as food, drinks, household products, skincare, personal needs, and others. Consumer desires can be identified based on price grouping, product quality, service quality, social media marketing, and brand/reputation. Reputation is an image attached to a product or company that gives a strong impression of the name. Reputation is an image or sign of the overall value recognized by a group of people or consumers because consumers do not have personal experience with sellers when shopping, so reputation is important in building consumer trust in sellers (Angraini Rafika & Kurniawati Tri, 2022)

Knowing the needs or desires of consumers is important because the success of a business depends on customer satisfaction, therefore, to provide services that are in accordance with consumer desires, it is necessary to know the needs of consumers so as to generate customer loyalty to the supermarket and repeat sales in the long term, customers also have a reason to continue buying products at their favorite supermarket compared to competing products.

As time goes by, more and more minimarkets are opened in Batam City and the development of minimarket franchises such as Indomaret & Alfamart which affect supermarket income and competition in the retail business will be increasingly tight. Therefore,

companies need to know the needs and desires of customers or potential customers to develop products/services that are more in line with consumer expectations. This can increase customer satisfaction, build loyalty, and strengthen the company's position in the market. In addition, a deep understanding of customers also helps in developing effective marketing strategies. To find out the needs or desires of consumers, companies need to pay attention to several things such as price, market orientation, brand loyalty, product quality, social media marketing, service quality, and stock.

Price is the amount/value of money that must be paid by customers to obtain a product or service. Price includes pricing strategies, discounts, special offers, and all aspects related to the economic value of a product or service in the market. Price is one of the elements of the marketing mix that generates revenue, other elements generate costs. Price is the easiest element to adjust in a marketing program, product features, channels, and even communication take a lot of time. Price is the amount of money set by the seller of a good or service and paid by the buyer of the good or service to meet the needs and desires of the person who buys it (Sukmawati Anggita & Gischa Serafica, 2023).

Market Orientation is an approach that emphasizes a deep understanding of customer needs, wants, and behavior as the center of all company activities. Market orientation is the opposite of production orientation where companies focus more on production efficiency and increasing production volume while production orientation emphasizes making as many efficient products as possible and market orientation emphasizes understanding and meeting customer needs as efficiently as possible. Market orientation is important in an increasingly changing and dynamic economy because it enables companies to remain relevant and compete effectively in changing markets (Nasrudin Ahmad, 2022).

According to Jico et al. (2019), brand loyalty or loyalty to an image/brand is the level of customer loyalty or trust in a particular brand or product. When consumers have brand loyalty, consumers tend to choose and buy products from that market consistently even though there are various choices. Brand loyalty is a valuable component for a company because it can provide a stable and reliable customer base. Gaining brand loyalty from consumers requires ongoing efforts in providing consistent product or service quality, building a positive brand image and maintaining good relationships with customers.

Product quality refers to the level of excellence or quality of a product so that it can be seen to what extent the product meets or exceeds customer expectations and whether the products offered or sold meet the standards set by the manufacturer or industry. Product quality is the key to the success of a brand or company, customers tend to choose products that offer high quality because they provide better value in the long term. Therefore, companies tend to invest in research and development, quality control, and innovation to ensure that their products maintain or improve quality (Kuswibowo et al., 2020).

Social media marketing is a marketing strategy that uses social media platforms to promote products, services, or brands and interact with target audiences. The goal of social media marketing is to increase brand presence, generate traffic to websites, and engage with customers through various social media platforms. The benefits of social media marketing include being able to reach target audiences directly, building brand awareness, increasing customer engagement, and providing opportunities to interact directly with consumers. Success in social media marketing requires creativity, consistency, and a good understanding of specific social media platforms (Othysalonika et al., 2022).

Service quality is the level of excellence or quality of service provided by a company to its customers. Service quality is a key factor in building positive relationships with customers and creating satisfying experiences. Service quality is subjective and can vary between individuals. Service quality is often based on the customer's personal experience and the extent to which the service provided meets or exceeds customer expectations. Service quality is key to maintaining and strengthening customer relationships and supporting long-term success for a company (Djunaedi & Rahman, 2023). Stock or inventory of goods in a company are goods owned by the company to be sold or used in the production process. This inventory can be in the form of finished goods ready for sale, raw materials to be processed into final products, or goods in the production process. Inventory of goods is an important part of the supply chain and operational management of a company. Effective operational management of inventory can help companies avoid stock shortages that can hamper production or maintain excess inventory that can drain resources (Desy, 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Relationship between Price variables and Market Orientation Market orientation is a business approach that focuses on how to meet and understand customer needs, the relationship between price and market orientation to determine the extent to which

the pricing policy of a product or service describes the company's understanding of customer needs, desires, and behavior (Liantika, 2022). By understanding customer needs and market conditions well, companies can develop price revenue strategies that are more in line with market demands, market orientation can help create a balance between price, value, and customer satisfaction.

The relationship between brand loyalty and market orientation is interrelated because both focus on customers and understand consumer needs and wants. By having a strong market orientation, companies can more effectively build and maintain brand loyalty. The combination of deep understanding of customers, responding to market needs, and offering products or services that meet customer expectations can build a good long-term relationship between brand image and consumers (Maulidiyah, 2022).

The relationship between Product quality and social media marketing can be said to be interrelated because product quality can have a significant impact on brand reputation shared through social media. Product quality directly affects customer reviews and if the product is good quality, customers tend to give positive reviews. With social media, consumer reviews and thoughts can spread quickly, influencing public perception of a brand. Therefore, maintaining high product quality and ensuring a satisfying customer experience is very important in social media marketing (Sapitri & Malik Akbar Rohandi, 2022).

The relationship between social media marketing and market orientation is interrelated because information obtained through social media can help companies adjust marketing strategies and products to better reflect customer needs and expectations. In addition, data obtained through social media can be considered a form of dynamic market research that helps companies understand trends, consumer behavior, and responses to marketing. By integrating social media marketing with market orientation, companies can gain better insight into the market, increase customer engagement, and respond to market changes more flexibly (Yadi Heryadi et al., 2023).

The relationship between service quality and market orientation creates an important link in efforts to achieve customer satisfaction and understand market needs. Market orientation promotes an understanding of customer needs, wants, and behavior with high service quality can ensure that services are designed to meet customer needs. Good market orientation allows companies to respond to market changes quickly. Responsive service quality can adjust services according to changing customer or market needs. The relationship between service quality and market orientation can direct companies towards better service, respond to market changes, and meet customer expectations so that they can benefit the company in the long term (Susanto, 2020).

The relationship between stock (inventory of goods) and market orientation involves how companies manage and organize inventory to meet customer needs and expectations. Companies that have good market orientation will tend to understand customer demand and preferences so that inventory can be adjusted to effectively meet customer needs, and a good market orientation allows companies to respond quickly to changes in market demand. The integration of inventory management and market orientation creates an environment where companies can more effectively meet customer expectations and respond to market dynamics. A deep understanding of customer needs and market involvement can shape a smarter and more responsive inventory strategy (Octavia & Sriyudha, 2020).

Figure 1. Research Model

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative research method or scientific approach that uses numerical or quantitative data to collect information, analyze the results of hypothesis tests and relationships between variables. This quantitative research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to the entire community of Batam City. In this study there are 7 variables, namely 5 independent variables, 1 mediation variable, and 1 dependent variable.

The data used in this study are primary data, this primary data was collected using a questionnaire via Google Form and distributed online via social media platforms. The population in this study were supermarket visitors in Batam City. This study used purposive sampling which is a sampling technique where researchers select samples based on knowledge of the characteristics that are relevant to this study (Mukti et al., 2021).

This study uses a Likert scale, to measure indicators of existing variables to determine the level of opinion or perception of a person towards a statement. The Likert scale consists of a series of statements followed by a series of response options arranged in stages, such as:

- a. Strongly Disagree (STS)
- b. Disagree (ST)
- c. Agree (S)
- d. Strongly Agree (SS)
- e. Completely Agree (SS)

According to Hair et al. (2022) the number of respondents must be at least 100 or more, in general it is recommended to achieve a sample size of at least five times greater than the number of statement indicators analyzed and have a ratio of 10:1. In this study, there were 26 statement indicators, so the number of samples required was at least 260 respondents and the questionnaires distributed reached 266 respondents. Then the results of the questionnaire will be examined using the SPSS system and the PLS system.

In this study, determining the definition of variables is an important step to ensure the credibility of the research method and results. There are 7 variables involved, namely price, brand loyalty, product quality, service quality, stock, social media marketing, and market orientation. The following are details regarding the operational definition of each variable.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The survey results show that this study is dominated by women at 54.5% while men are 45.5%. This data shows that most respondents are aged 18 to 25 years with jobs as private employees who have an income of around Rp. 4,500,000 - Rp. 6,000,000 who often shop and visit the Batam City Supermarket

Table 1. Respondent Profile

Criteria	Category	Total	Percentage
Gender	Man	121	45,5%
	Woman	145	54,5%
Total		266	100%
Age	<18 year	10	3,8%
	18 – 25 year	132	49,6%
	26 – 32 year	88	33,1%
	33 – 40 year	27	10,2%
	>40 year	9	3,3%
Total		266	100%
Education	Elementary school	3	1,1%
	Junior high school	8	3%
	Senior high school	116	43,6%
	Bachelor	127	47,7%
	Magister	12	4,6%

Criteria	Category	Total	Percentage
Total		266	100%
Job	Student	6	2,3%
	Lecture	56	20,8%
	Entrepreneurs	42	15,7%
	Employee	147	55,5%
	Housewife	13	4,9%
	Others	2	0,8%
Total		266	100%
Monhtly Income	< Rp. 4.500.000	50	18,8%
	Rp. 4.500.001 - Rp. 6.000.000	114	42,9%
	Rp. 6.500.001 - Rp. 8.000.000	39	14,7%
	Rp. 8.500.001 - Rp. 10.000.000	28	10,5%
	> Rp. 10.000.001	35	13,1%
Total		266	100%

Source: Data Processed (2024)

It is known that the validity, reliability, and AVE test research using the smartPLS system can be said that the above data results are accurate. Based on the rule of thumb, the outer loading value must be more than 0.6 so that the indicators of each variable can be said to be valid, the price variable shows the outer loading value ranging from 0.747 to 0.827, the brand loyalty variable 0.731 to 0.873, the product quality variable 0.783 to 0.856, the service quality variable ranges from 0.793 to 0.843, the stock variable 0.746 to 0.842, the social media marketing variable ranges from 0.839 to 0.882, and for the market orientation variable ranges from 0.804 to 0.838. Testing on the composite reliability of each variable must be more than 0.7 to be said to be reliable, the composite reliability value of each variable can be said to have met the criteria with a price variable value of 0.834, a brand loyalty variable of 0.857, a product quality variable of 0.882, a service quality variable of 0.908, a stock variable of 0.840, a social media marketing variable of 0.894, and a market orientation variable of 0.862 all variables are said to be reliable because the able ki value is more than 0.7 and meets the criteria. In the AVE (Average Variance Extract) test to be said to be valid, the AVE value must be above 0.5 and the AVE value for the price variable is 0.626, the brand loyalty variable is 0.668, the product quality variable is 0.653, the service quality variable is 0.663, the stock variable is 0.637, the social media marketing variable is 0.738, and the market orientation variable is 0.675 and the AVE in the able above is in accordance with the criteria because the value of the variable is above 0.5 and all variables are said to be valid.

The hypothesis tested can be said to be significant if the t-statistic value is more than 1.96 and the p-value is less than 0.05 (Hasan & Lim, 2024). Based on the output produced, it can be concluded that:

H1: The Price variable has a significant positive effect on Market Orientation.

Price has a positive and significant effect on market orientation. This is proven by the t-statistic value of 3.101 which means > 1.96 and a p-value of 0.002 which means < 0.05 which indicates that price can increase market orientation. This is in line with previous studies which state that there is a significant and positive relationship between price and market orientation. (Fahlefi Diva Riza, 2021; Kannebley Júnior et al., 2023; Gul et al., 2021). Competitive prices can attract more consumers, so that prices that are too high can make consumers switch to competitors, this is important for markets whose orientation focuses on consumer needs.

H2: Brand Loyalty variable does not have a significant effect on Market Orientation

Brand Loyalty does not have a significant effect on market orientation. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 1.236 which means < 1.96 and a p-value of 0.217 which means > 0.05 which indicates that the impact of customer loyalty to a brand on market orientation is not strong enough. This contrasts with previous studies which stated that there is a significant relationship between brand loyalty and market orientation (Khan et al., 2021; M. R. Khan & Ghouri 2018; Drennan et al., 2023). Market orientation focuses on fulfilling consumer desires and needs, although brand quality is important, market orientation emphasizes more on how products or services meet consumer expectations and preferences, not only based on brand quality.

H3: Product Quality variable has a significant effect on Social Media Marketing

Product quality has a positive and significant effect on social media marketing. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 4.304 which means > 1.96 and p-value 0.000 which means < 0.05 which shows that product quality can improve social media marketing. This is in line with previous research which states that there is a significant relationship between product quality and social media marketing ((Sapitri & Malik Akbar Rohandi Management Study Program, 2022). Good and high product quality can result in greater customer satisfaction so that satisfied customers will share positive experiences through social media, and this can increase credibility and attract new customers

H4: Social Media Marketing Variables Do Not Have a Significant Effect on Market Orientation

Social media marketing does not have a significant effect on market orientation. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 1.325 which means < 1.96 and p-value 0.186 > 0.05 which indicates that the impact of social media marketing on market orientation is not strong enough. This contrasts with previous studies which stated that there is a significant relationship between social media marketing and market orientation (Kartika, 2021); Galib et al., 2022; (Kristinae Vivy & Sahay Meitiana, 2019). Although product content and product information through social media are interesting, social media marketing often focuses on one-way communication and to understand the market and customers, companies need to have more in-depth direct interactions with consumers.

H5: Service Quality Variables Do Not Have a Significant Effect on Market Orientation

Service quality does not have a significant effect on market orientation. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 1.773 which means < 1.96 and a p-value of 0.077 > 0.05 which indicates that the impact of service quality on market orientation is not strong enough. This contrasts with previous research which stated that there is a significant positive relationship between service quality and market orientation (Susanto, 2020). Although the quality of a company's service is important, not all companies place service quality as a top priority, there are some companies that prioritize product quality, price, and innovation. Service quality may not be enough to differentiate a company and significantly influence market orientation if all competitors provide similar services.

H6: Stock variable has a positive effect on Market orientation

Stocks have a positive and significant effect on market orientation. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 5.138 which means > 1.96 and a p-value of 0.000 which means < 0.05 which indicates that a company's stock can increase market orientation. This is in line with previous research which states that there is a significant relationship between stock and market orientation (Octavia & Sriyudha, 2020). Market orientation prioritizes meeting customer needs and desires. The availability of sufficient and timely products is very important to ensure that customers can get the products they want and need. If the product stock is insufficient, customers will feel disappointed and switch to other competitors, which affects market orientation.

H7: Price variable does not have a significant effect on Market Orientation mediated by Social Media Marketing

Price does not have a significant effect on market orientation mediated by social media marketing. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 1.265 which means < 1.96 and the p-value of 0.206 which means > 0.05 which indicates that the impact of price on market orientation mediated by social media marketing variables is not strong enough. This contrasts with previous research which states that there is a significant relationship between price and market orientation (Puspaningrum, 2020); Joensuu-Salo et al., 2018). Many market-oriented companies use a differentiation strategy that does not depend on price, many customers are willing to pay more if it matches their expectations. There are companies that increase market orientation by providing relevant value to consumers that is more than just pricing.

H8: Product Quality variable does not have a significant effect on Market Orientation through Social Media Marketing

Product quality does not have a significant effect on market orientation mediated by social media marketing. This is evidenced by the t-statistic value of 1.200 which means < 1.96 and the p-value of 1.231 which means > 0.05 which indicates that the impact of product quality on market orientation mediated by social media marketing is not strong enough. This is in contrast to previous studies which stated that there is a significant relationship between product quality and market orientation mediated by social media marketing (Emil & Sari, 2022); Alwi et al., 2023). Social media is often formed with interesting content, viral trends, or short reviews so that this affects the quality of the product that is not visible and not easily evaluated through posts. Consumers may be more interested in other aspects such as design or creative promotions and this influences market orientation.

R-Square Test Results

Table 2. R Square Results

Variabel	R Squares	R Square Adj
Market Orientation	0,657	0,650
Social Media Marketing	0,471	0,467

Source: Data Processed (2024)

Based on table 2, the test conducted in this study determining the R Square value shows that Price (X1) & Stock (X5) have an effect on Market Orientation (Y) which has a value of 0.657 or 65.7% while the remaining 34.3% is influenced by other factors that are not included in this research model. Social Media Marketing (Z) is influenced by Product Quality (X3) with a value of 0.471 or 47.1% and the remaining 52.9% is influenced by other factors that are not included in this model.

CONCLUSION

In this study it can be concluded that in the retail industry such as supermarkets, price cannot increase social media marketing and market orientation, low prices cannot increase social media marketing because even though the price is low, but the quality of the product is not guaranteed, it cannot create better social media marketing and cannot meet customer expectations that affect market orientation. Brand loyalty cannot affect market orientation because there are many factors that can affect the company's strategy in meeting market needs. Products with high quality tend to get positive reviews that increase the effectiveness of social media marketing. Although social media is an important marketing platform, the impact on market orientation is limited because market orientation requires a deeper approach to customer needs. It can be concluded that market orientation is influenced by various factors such as price and stock have a significant effect on market orientation while other factors such as brand loyalty, service quality, and social media marketing have a more varied effect depending on the context and strategy used by the company. This study has limitations because it only focuses on the variables of price, brand loyalty, product quality, service quality, stock, and social media marketing on market orientation. Further research is suggested to add several other variables such as customer satisfaction (Wandi Yulfis et al., 2020) and purchase intention (Kesumahati, 2021) with the aim of identifying other factors that influence market orientation and expanding the understanding of future research.

REFERENCES

1. Alwi, N. A., Firman, A., Hidayat, M., & Razak, M. (2023). *Peran Positioning Strategi Dalam Memediasi Orientasi Pasar dan Kualitas Produk dan Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Pemasaran*. <https://e-jurnal.nobel.ac.id/index.php/akmen>
2. Anggraini Rafika, & Kurniawati Tri. (2022). *Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Perilaku Pembelian Konsumen di Toko Online*. *Jurnal Salingka Nagari*. moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjsn.pjj.unp.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Fjsn%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F7%2F15
3. Desy. (2023). *Pengertian Stok Barang Persediaan Adalah? Berikut Penjelasannya!* <https://www.jurnal.id/id/blog/pahamitentang-stok-barang-persediaan/>
4. Djunaedi, N., & Rahman, M. A. (2023). Pengaruh Service Quality terhadap Customer Satisfaction pada Layanan Jasa Go-Jek di Kota Palopo. *Jurnal Manajemen Perbankan Keuangan Nitro*, 6(1), 26–38. <https://doi.org/10.56858/JMPKN.V6I1.89>
5. Drennan, T., Nordman, E. R., & Safari, A. (2023). *Does a Sustainable Orientation Affect Global Consumers' Relationships with International Online Brands?* (pp. 219–236). <https://doi.org/10.1108/s1876-066x20230000037012>
6. Emil, K., & Sari, D. K. (2022). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Orientasi Pasar dan Penjualan Adaptif Terhadap Kinerja Pemasarn Melalui Keunggulan Bersaing Pada Mitra Usaha PT. Natural Nusantara di Kecamatan Prigen Pasuruan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan*, 1(3), 441–453. <https://doi.org/10.55606/jimak.v1i3.568>
7. Fahlefi Diva Riza. (2021). Pengaruh tata letak, kualitas, harga, dan kepuasan konsumen terhadap orientasi pasar. *Jurnal Keuangan Dan Bisnis*, 19(1). file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/150-Article Text-822-2-10-20220729-1.pdf
8. Galib, M., Haerani, S., Maming, J., & Munir, A. R. (2022). *The Effect of Using Social Media Marketing and Market*

Orientation on the Performance of Culinary MSMEs in Makassar (Vol. 1, Issue 2).

9. Gul, R. F., Liu, D., Jamil, K., Baig, S. A., Awan, F. H., & Liu, M. (2021). Linkages between market orientation and brand performance with positioning strategies of significant fashion apparels in Pakistan. *Fashion and Textiles*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-021-00254-9>
10. Hair, J. F., January, B., Tomas, G., Hult, M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354331182>
11. Hasan, G., & Lim, J. (2024). The Influence of Service Quality Factors on Customer Satisfaction in the Banking Sector in Batam City. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 14(1), 369–380. <https://doi.org/10.29322/ijsrp.14.01.2024.p14537>
12. Jico, P. T., Jakarta, A., Mahanani, E., & Sari, B. (2019). *Analisis Pengaruh Brand Awareness*. 16(02).
13. Joensuu-Salo, S., Sorama, K., Viljamaa, A., & Varamäki, E. (2018). Firm performance among internationalized smes: The interplay of market orientation, marketing capability and digitalization. *Administrative Sciences*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci8030031>
14. Kannebley Júnior, S., Prince, D. de, & Silva, D. Q. P. da. (2023). Pricing-to-market of Brazilian exports: a case of vehicle currency invoicing. *Economia*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECON-01-2023-0010>
15. Kartika, H. (2021). International Journal of Social and management Studies (IJOMas) The Role of Social media Marketing Product Innovation and Market Orientation on Marketing Performance : An Empirical Study on SMES in Banten. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies (IJOSMAS)*, 02(05).
16. Kesumahati, E. (2021). *Analisis pengaruh brand equity , e-wom , dan brand image dari social media terhadap purchase intention restoran fast food di kota batam*. 1(1). <https://ojs.digitalartisan.co.id/index.php/conescintech/article/view/5851/1793>
17. Khan, M. R., & Ghouri, A. M. (2018). Enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty through Customer-Defined Market Orientation and Customer Inspiration: A Critical Literature Review. In *International Business Education Journal* (Vol. 11, Issue 1). <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3303633>
18. Khan, N. R., Ul Abedin, Z., Ghouri, A. M., Karachi, P., Specialist, S., Bank, M., & Abedin, Z. U. (2021). (In) Direct Effects of Customer-Defined Market Orientation on Brand Loyalty through Purchase Intention and Brand Image: A Parallel Mediation Approach. In *The Lahore Journal of Business* (Vol. 9, Issue 2).
19. Kristinae Vivvy, & Sahay Meitiana. (2019). *Pengaruh Social Media, Learning Orientation dan Market Oorientation Terhadap Marketing Capabilities UKM Kerupuk IkanSaluang di Kalimantan Tengah*.
20. Kuswibowo, C., Enggar Tyasti, A., & Febrianto, D. (2020). The Effect of Product quality and brand Image on Customer satisfaction. *Jakarta Selatan*, 34. [moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.poltekapp.ac.id%2Findex.php%2FSNMIP%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F789%2F96](https://www.moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.poltekapp.ac.id%2Findex.php%2FSNMIP%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F789%2F96)
21. Liantika, E. (2022). *Pengaruh Orientasi Pasar Kualitas Produk dan harga Kompetitif terhadap Kinerja Pemasaran UMKM Bidang Fashion di Pontianak*. 6(9). [moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.widyadharma.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Fbisma%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F2715%2F4073%2F18194](https://www.moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.widyadharma.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Fbisma%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F2715%2F4073%2F18194)
22. Liusudarso, T., Girsang, J., & Situmeang, A. (2022). *Perlindungan Hukum Konsumen Muslim Atas Produk Pangan Tidak Bersertifikat Halal Di Kota Batam*. 6(2), 2022. <http://publishing-widyagama.ac.id/ejournal-v2/index.php/jhls/>
23. Maulidiyah, W. (2022). *Pengaruh orientasi pasar dan kualitas produk terhadap Kinerja Pemasaran Home Industri Kerudung Kabupaten Gresik*. [moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.unesa.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Fjptn%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F41872%2F36662%2F](https://www.moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjournal.unesa.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Fjptn%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F41872%2F36662%2F)
24. Mukti, A., Tinggi, S., Bima, I. E., & Aprianti, K. (2021). Pengaruh kualitas playanan dan harga terhadap keputusan pembelian pada kedai kirani coffee. *Jurnal Bina Manajemen*, 10(1), 229–245. <file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/163-Article Text-780-2-10-20210927.pdf>

25. Nasrudin Ahmad. (2022). *Orientasi Pasar: Cara Kerja, Keunggulan dan Kelemahan [2023]*.
<https://cerdasco.com/orientasi-pasar/>
26. Octavia, A., & Sriayudha, Y. (2020). *Strategi orientasi Pasar Konsep dan Implentasi Bagi usaha Kecil dan Menengah*.
www.salimmedia.com
27. Othysalonika, Wahib Muhaimin, A., & Faizal, F. (2022). *Pengaruh Socail Media marketing Terhadap Minat dan keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Pada Usaha Makanan Sehat di Kota Malang*. 6, 1134–1146.
<https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jepa.2022.006.03.32>
28. Puspaningrum, A. (2020). Market Orientation, Competitive Advantage and Marketing Performance of Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs). *Journal of Economics, Business, & Accountancy Ventura*, 23(1), 19–27.
<https://doi.org/10.14414/jebav.v23i1.1847>
29. Sapitri, T., & Malik Akbar Rohandi Prodi Manajemen, M. (2022). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk dan Social Media Marketing terhadap Keputusan Pembelian di X Shop di Kota Bandung. *Bandung Conference Series: Business and Management*, 2(1), 25–31. <https://doi.org/10.29313/BCSBM.V2I1.239>
30. Sukmawati Anggita, & Gischa Serafica. (2023). *Pengertian Harga Menurut Ahli: Tujuan, Jenis dan Contohnya*.
<https://www.kompas.com/skola/read/2023/03/16/060000469/pengertian-harga-menurut-ahli-tujuan-jenis-dan-contohnya>
31. Susanto, B. (2020). Pengaruh Orientasi Pasar, Kualitas Layanan, Kepuasan Konsumen Dan Keunggulan Bersaing Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada King Perabot Kota Pinang. *Ekonomi Bisnis Manajemen Dan Akuntansi (EBMA)*, 1(2), 2020. [moz-extension://f73d2a10-6f59-405a-91eb-5f4179c00e86/enhanced-reader.html?openApp&pdf=https%3A%2F%2Fjurnal.ulb.ac.id%2Findex.php%2Ffebma%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F3135%2F2486](https://doi.org/10.29313/BCSBM.V2I1.239)
32. Vicky, & Rustam Triana Ananda. (2023). *Pengatuh variasi Produk Brand Image dan Kualitas Informasi terhadap Minat beli di Bestmart Supermarket Batam*. <https://stiealwashliyahsibolga.ac.id/jurnal/index.php/jesya/article/view/1099/655>
33. Wandu Yulfis, Zainal Veithzal Rivai, Arafah Willy, & Subagja Iwan Kurniawan. (2020). *The effect of service and product quality on customer satisfaction through customer awareness of islamic banks in west sumatera, indonesia*.
<https://mgesjournals.com/hssr/article/view/hssr.2020.8182/2789>
34. Yadi Heryadi, D., Ekowati, D., & Chusumastuti, D. (2023). *Pengaruh Kehadiran Media Sosial, Orientasi Pasar Terhadap Kinerja UMKM di Jawa Barat*. 5(1), 94–107. <http://bisnisman.nusaputra.ac.id>

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